

VAKA TAKDİMİ

CASE REPORT

METHYL ALCOHOL INTOXICATION; CASE REPORT

Dilek Atik¹, Aslihan Onuralp¹, Fulya Köse¹, H.Seyma Akça¹, Cesareddin Dikmetas¹

¹ Karamanoğlu Mehmetbey University Faculty of Medicine Department of Emergency Medicine

ABSTRACT

Methyl alcohol is obtained through the distillation of harcoal. It is industrially used and legally sold, due to its solvent effect. It is cheap and easy to access when compared to ethyl alcohol, causes methyl alcohol to be used as an alcoholic beverage by unconscious sections of the society. Even a very small amount of methyl alcohol like 8-10 ml shows a toxic effect. a 1ml/kg dose is fatal. Following methyl alcohol inhalation, the clinic may be quiet until toxic metabolites occur. Therefore, we thought it is a great case to show how important the ability to take anamnesis is for medicine.

A 40-year-old male patient applied with complaints of not being able to maintain his balance and blurred vision especially in his right eye that started 1 day ago. Application vitals fever: 36.5°C heart rate :80rate/min blood pressure :110/70 mmHg SPO2: 92. Patient was taking treatment due to alcohol-due liver-s for 3 years and still use alcohol. He has had difficulty in maintaining balance for 2 years, but he fell fall 1 day before the application. GCS: 15. The motor power was natural in all the extremities. Cerebellar examination was natural. The neck did not have strength. Light reflexes were natural in the left eye and decreased in the right eyes. The other system examination is normal. And the magnetic resonance (MR) was wanted for imaginering. It was normal.

Patients coming due to methyl alcohol intoxication mostly unconsciously applied, our patient's GCS: 15. Due to that, we didn't talk to the patient him and his history from his history. Formic acid in methyl alcohol intoxication mostly apply with complaints of visual disorders and headache in the early period. In our case, the main complaint was loss of balance and we learned that there was a visual disorder in the detailed inquiry. Due to measurement of methyl alcohol at the bedboard and in the laboratory, communication skills for clinical information and consultaneous physician and communication skills with physicians, because methyl alcohol cannot be measured mostly in emergency departments in our country it is supplied. Physicians in the emergency department should consider methyl alcohol intoxication, especially in the presence of visional disorder, headache, loss of balance or unexplained acidosis, and should improve their skills in questioning patients.

Key Words: Methyl alcohol, blurred vision, Intoxication

Correspondence to: Dilek Atik

¹Karamanoğlu Mehmetbey University Faculty of Medicine Department of Emergency Medicine

E-mail: dr.dilekgok82@hotmail.com

Orcid: 0000-0002-3270-8711

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INTRODUCTION

Methyl alcohol is obtained through the distillation of harcoal (1,2,3). It is industrially used and legally sold, due to its solvent effect(1). It is cheap and easy to access when compared to ethyl alcohol, causes methyl alcohol to be used as an alcoholic beverage by unconscious sections of the society(1). Even a very small amount of methyl alcohol like 8-10 ml shows a toxic effect. a 1ml/kg dose is fatal(1). Following methyl alcohol inhalation, the clinic may be quiet until toxic metabolites occur(4). Therefore, we thought it is a great case to show how important the ability to take anamnesis is for medicine.

CASE REPORT

A 40-year-old male patient applied with complaints of not being able to maintain his balance and blurred vision especially in his right eye that started 1 day ago. Application vitals T:36.5 nb:80 TA:110/70 SPO2: 92. Patient was taking treatment due to alcohol-due liver-s for 3 years and still use alcohol. He has had difficulty in maintaining balance for 2 years, but he fell fall 1 day before the application. GCS: 15. The motor power was natural in all the extremities. Cerebellar examination was natural. The neck did not have strength. Light reflexes were natural in the left ey and decreased in the right eyes. Examinations have been taken. MR done. In biochemistry, Glucose:118 mg/dl, Urea:16.2 mg/dl, EGFR:103.67 Creatinin :0.92 mg/dl , AST:119 U/l, ALT:52 U/l, ALP: 121 U/l, GGT:221.9 U/l, ALBUMIN: 33.4g/l, AMYLASE:72 U/l, Total Bilirubin:3.18 mg/Dl, Direct Bilirubin :0.83 mg/dl, Indirect Bilirubin 2.35mg/dl, CK:534 U/l, CK-MB:16.8 U/l , CRP:1.1 mg/l, Na:134.7 mmol/l, K:3.47 mmol/l, Troponine:50.11 ng/l , INR:1.33, APTT:29.7 Sec , PT: 11.9 Sec, ETHANOL: 2.45 mg /dl.In Hemogram WBC: 9.16 K/uL, HGB:14.7 G/DL , HCT:43.0%. In Blood Gas:, PH:7.41, PO2:62.8 mmHg, PCO2:30.4mmHg, HCO3:18.8 mmol/l , LACTATE:8.69 mmol/l.The MR is normal. When the patient's anamnesis is deepended, it was learned that he has a history of use of fake alcohol without a bandrool 2 days ago. 250 cc sf iv infusion 500cc 5% dextrose started. available information was transferred to the anesthesia doctor. consulted with the poison counseling center. Poison counseling center consider that the patient be given to dialysis if he has acidosis, ethyl and there is any disorder in consciousness and clinical status, that visual disorder can be permanent and if it continues, the ophthalmologist consultancy is needed. The patient was given intensive care for follow-up and treatment. Respiratory difficulty and bradycardia developed at the follow-up of the patient and he was intubated.

DISCUSSION

Patients coming due to methyl alcohol intoxication mostly unconsciously applied(5), our patient's GCS: 15 SO we could talk and we learnt that he drunk metyl alcohol . Formic acid in methyl alcohol intoxication mostly apply with complaints of visual disorders and headache in the early period(4). In our case, the main complaint was loss of balance and we learned that there was a visual disorder in the detailed inquiry. Due to measurement of methyl alcohol at the bedboard and in the laboratory, communication skills for clinical information and consultaneous physician and

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All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding this manuscript.

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